

Participation of male commercial motorcyclists in pregnancy and delivery care in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Male partners' involvement in pregnancy and delivery care is critical for improving mother and child health outcomes, especially in areas with high maternal death rates, such as Nigeria. This study investigates the role of male commercial motorcyclists in pregnancy and delivery care in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Nigeria.

Material and methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out on 453 male commercial motorcyclists in Ibadan North Local Government Area. The participants were married men aged 18 and up, whose wives had given birth during the previous two years. Data was gathered using pre-tested semi-structured interviewer-administered questionnaires and analyzed with IBM SPSS version 22.0, which displayed descriptive statistics in tables and charts. The chi-square test and binary logistic regression were used to determine determinants of active participation in pregnancy and delivery care.

Results: Approximately 67.8% of respondents were actively engaged in pregnancy and delivery care. Financial help for antenatal care (94.7%), delivery transport (87.2%), and attendance at antenatal sessions (59.8%) were the most commonly reported areas of engagement. Notably, 49.4% of dads were there throughout their child's delivery. Men in monogamous relationships are significantly more likely to be actively involved than those in polygamous relationships (OR: 2.43, 95% CI: 1.37-4.31).

Conclusion: Two-thirds of respondents actively cared for their wives during pregnancy and delivery. To increase male engagement, interventions should promote supportive family situations and improve knowledge and attitudes towards maternal healthcare.

Keywords: Male involvement, Maternal care, Pregnancy, Delivery care, Motorcyclists, Nigeria

Introduction

Quality care for women during pregnancy and delivery is a critical component of the sexual and reproductive healthcare continuum (1). The survival of women throughout pregnancy and childbirth is also regarded as a fundamental human right that must be protected by providing the means and infrastructure required to achieve it (2). Male involvement, including male responsibility and participation, is a critical strategy for enhancing maternal health. Its roles in enhancing maternal health have been stressed, in addition to its recognition as one of the ways that might be explored in maternal mortality reduction (3,4).

Maternal mortality is unacceptably high in many parts of the world, despite continued efforts. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that over 287,000 women would die during and after pregnancy and delivery in 2020 (5). Almost 95% of maternal deaths occurred in low- and lower-middle-income countries, with most being preventable (5). According to the 2018 National Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS), Nigeria has the fourth highest maternal mortality ratio (MMR) in the world, at 512 per 100,000 live births (6). Efforts to reduce MMR are critical for meeting the first target of the third Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 3), which is to have less than 70 maternal deaths per 100,000 live births by 2030 (7).

Many women with children rely heavily on their male spouses or fathers for support. Their involvement in pregnancy, labor, and the postpartum period improves a variety of mother and child health outcomes, as well as overall family well-being. Previous research has described some of the advantages of male involvement in maternal health, such as increased access to antenatal care, more skilled birth deliveries, greater access to modern contraceptive methods, and improved cognitive and socio-emotional development of children (8-10). Furthermore, husbands' involvement in pregnancy care can help reduce non-medical and indirect causes of maternal mortality, such as the delay in recognizing pregnancy-related symptoms and getting to a healthcare facility (11).

A research conducted in Tanzania found that 69% of men participated in prenatal care. More than two-thirds (76%) of nursing moms reported receiving physical, psychological, and financial support from their spouses, and the majority of women (85%) attended four or more prenatal appointments (12). This emphasized how men's roles can improve results for their pregnant women. Another study conducted in Ibadan, Nigeria, found that 56.6% of husbands were involved in pregnancy care and delivery in some capacity (8).

Although the importance of male participation in pregnancy and delivery care is becoming more widely recognized, the incidence remains low, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria with high MMR (13). Male commercial motorcyclists were investigated for the socioeconomic and occupational characteristics that distinguished this group. They were a visible, organized demographic within the larger male population, confronting obstacles substantially different from men in formal employment. This group was particularly typical of low-income, informal-sector workers who commonly faced institutional impediments to adopting preventative health practices.

As a result, the purpose of this study is to offer essential baseline data on critical features of male engagement in pregnancy and delivery care among commercial motorcyclists in the Ibadan North Local Government Area (LGA), Nigeria. The information supplied can be utilized to further research into the scope and advantages of male participation. It will also identify opportunities for intervention to increase male participation and hence improve mother and child health, particularly among informal workers in various low-resource contexts.

Materials and methods

This descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out at Ibadan North LGA. This LGA is one of eleven in the Ibadan metropolitan region, which is Sub-Saharan Africa's largest indigenous city and the capital of Oyo State in Southwest Nigeria. Ibadan North LGA's administrative headquarters are at Bodija town. The LGA has an area of 132,500 square kilometers and has a population density of 22,670 people per square kilometer. The LGA's population in 2022 was estimated to be 440,400 using data from the 2006 census and a 2.3% growth rate (14). The area's population is primarily Yoruba. The study focused on male commercial motorcyclists who operated transit routes in Ibadan North LGA. Married men aged 18 and above, as well as men whose wives had given birth within the previous two years, met the inclusion requirements.

The sample size was derived using the cross-sectional study formula with the qualitative result ($N = Z^2pq/d^2$) (15) at a 95% confidence level and a prior study's estimated prevalence of men attending prenatal and delivery care of 34% (16). Assuming a 10% non-response rate, a sample size of 380 was calculated. Respondents were selected using a cluster sampling technique. Commercial motorcyclists in Ibadan North LGA operate from thirty-four units, and seventeen of these units (clusters) were selected using a simple random sample approach. All motorcyclists in the

chosen clusters who met the inclusion requirements were interviewed.

Trained research assistants collected data using a pre-tested, semi-structured interviewer-administered questionnaire. Data reliability was assured by translating the questionnaire from English to Yoruba, allowing participants to interact with the questions in their home language, and then back-translated into English to ensure that the meaning of each question was precisely preserved. In addition, the questionnaire was pre-tested with a similar demographic in Egbeda LGA, which is outside the study area, to detect any ambiguities that could influence results.

Dependent variables represented measurable characteristics of male involvement in prenatal and delivery care, such as ANC visit attendance, financial assistance, and emergency healthcare decision-making. The independent factors were age, education, income, and family size. The data was reviewed for mistakes and cleansed. Data was then entered electronically and analyzed using IBM SPSS version 22.0. Each segment was assessed on a three-point Likert scale. Each issue was rated using replies ranging from disagree to agree (agree=3, undecided=2, disagree=1). Higher ratings indicate increased knowledge and attitude. Responses to non-positive questions were scored in the same way that affirmative questions were scored, i.e., 1 was recorded as 3, and 3 as 1. The maximum score per question was three. Mean scores for each domain were calculated by summing the scores/questions for the participants and then used to disaggregate the knowledge and attitude scores of each domain into good and poor. Scores \geq mean were considered good, while scores $<$ mean were considered poor.

Descriptive statistics were used, and the results were presented as tables and charts. The chi-square test was performed to examine the relationship between male engagement and the independent variables. Multivariate binary logistic regression was performed to discover predictors of male involvement. Ethical approval was acquired from the Ethical Review Committee of the Oyo State Ministry of Health in Ibadan, and signed informed consents were obtained from all participants after the goal of the study was explained to them and confidentiality concerns were appropriately addressed. Confidentiality was maintained using secure data processing processes.

Results

A total of 453 male commercial motorcyclists were interviewed. Table 1 shows the sociodemographic features of the male commercial motorcyclists

interviewed. The respondents' average age was 34.2 ± 7.3 years, with 301 (66.4%) having completed secondary school education, 425 (93.8%) being married, 390 (86.1%) in a monogamous marriage, and 422 (93.2%) earning more than the minimum salary.

A large number of respondents (315, 69.6%) had adequate understanding of pregnancy and delivery care. Furthermore, 304 (67.1%) respondents had positive attitudes concerning pregnancy and delivery care (Figures 1 and 2).

Table 2 illustrates the areas of involvement of males in pregnancy and delivery care. Less than one-tenth (40, 8.8%) of respondents make arrangements for blood during their wives' pregnancy, while 395 (87.2%) and 364 (80.4%) make transportation available and set aside some money, respectively. A substantial number (94.7%, 59.8%, 63.1%, and 83.9%, respectively) paid for Antenatal Care (ANC) costs, attended ANC with their spouses, reminded their wives of medications, and were involved in the ANC facility selection process. Furthermore, 80.4%, 77.3%, 67.5%, 58.8%, and 49.4% of respondents financially supported their spouses during delivery, arranged for a helper after delivery, accompanied their wives to the postnatal care clinic, assisted their wives with home tasks, and attended the delivery.

Figure 3 shows that approximately two-thirds (307, 67.8%) of respondents were actively engaged in pregnancy and delivery care. Table 3 reveals a significant relationship between family type and active male involvement in pregnancy and delivery care ($p=0.002$). A greater proportion of monogamous couples (70.7%) were involved in their spouses' most recent pregnancy than polygamous couples (50.0%). Men with good knowledge (79.5%) were more likely to be actively involved in pregnancy and delivery care than men with weak knowledge (61.9%) ($p=0.030$). Similarly, men with a favorable attitude toward pregnancy and delivery care (74.7%) were more actively involved than men with an unfavorable view (63.9%) ($p=0.013$).

Table 4 demonstrates that men in monogamous relationships were 2.43 times more likely to actively participate in pregnancy and delivery care than men in polygamous relationships (OR: 2.43, 95%CI: 1.37-4.31). There were no other significant predictors of men's engagement in pregnancy and delivery care.

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of respondents

Variables	Frequency (453)	Percentage (100)
Age		
15-34	248	54.7
35-54	200	44.2
55-74	5	1.1
Level of education		
No formal education	5	1.1
Primary	123	27.2
Secondary	301	66.4
Tertiary	24	5.3
Marital status		
Married	425	93.8
Separated	14	3.1
Divorced	14	3.1
Family type		
Monogamous	390	86.1
Polygamous	63	13.9
Monthly income		
Below minimum wage	31	6.8
Above minimum wage	422	93.2

Table 2. Areas of involvement in pregnancy and delivery issues

Variable	Frequency* (n)	(%)
Involvement in choice of centre for ANC ¹	380	83.9
Payment for the cost of ANC ¹ bills	429	94.7
Attended ANC ¹ with wife	271	59.8
Reminded wife of medications	286	63.1
Helped wife with household chores	266	58.8
Provision of transport for delivery	395	87.2
Financial support towards delivery	364	80.4
Provided for blood	40	8.8
Present at delivery	224	49.4
Arrangement for a helper after delivery	350	77.3
Went to post-natal clinic with wife	306	67.5

* = Only positive responses

¹ = Antenatal Care

Table 3. Association between Socio-demographic characteristics, respondents' knowledge and attitude on involvement of male partners

Variable	Degree of Involvement		Total N (%)	X ²	P-value
	Some n (%)	Active n (%)			
Age (years)					
15-34	49 (19.8)	198 (80.2)	246 (100)	1.241	0.538
35 and above	40 (19.5)	165 (80.5)	205 (100)		
Marital status					
Married	82 (19.5)	339 (80.5)	421 (100)	3.279	0.351
Separated/Divorced	7 (22.6)	24 (77.4)	31 (100)		
Family type					
Monogamous	110 (29.3%)	265 (70.7%)	375 (100%)	10.12	0.002*
Polygamous	30 (50.0%)	30 (50.0%)	60 (100%)		
Education					
None and Primary	42 (33.6%)	83 (66.4%)	125 (100%)	0.177	0.915
Secondary	91 (31.7%)	196 (68.3%)	287 (100%)		
Tertiary	7 (30.4%)	16 (69.6%)	23 (100%)		
Knowledge score					
Good Knowledge	30 (20.5)	116 (79.5)	146 (100)	3.63	0.030*
Poor Knowledge	110 (38.1)	179 (61.9)	289 (100)		
Attitude scores					
Positive attitude	40 (25.3%)	118 (74.7%)	158 (100%)	5.36	0.013*
Negative attitude	100 (36.1%)	177 (63.9%)	277 (100%)		

Table 4. Predictors of active male involvement

Variables	Odds Ratio	95% CI	P-Value
Knowledge			
Good (ref)	1		
Poor	0.402	0.223- 1.722	0.062
Attitude			
Good	1.046	0.603 - 1.812	0.874
Poor (ref)	1		
Family Type			
Monogamous	2.43	1.372 - 4.315	0.002*
Polygamous (ref)	1		

Figure 1. Overall knowledge of pregnancy and delivery care among commercial motorcyclists

Figure 2. Overall attitude on pregnancy and delivery care among commercial motorcyclists

Figure 3. Overall involvement in pregnancy and delivery care

Discussion

This study looked at the involvement of male commercial motorcyclists in their partners' pregnancy and delivery care in the Ibadan North Local Government Area, and found significant levels of engagement in several aspects of maternal health. It also examined their knowledge and attitudes towards common pregnancy and delivery care issues, as well as potential connections and predictors of participation. Active involvement refers to the specific, supportive actions taken by men to promote maternal health during pregnancy and delivery, such as accompanying partners to antenatal care appointments, contributing financially to medical expenses, assisting with household duties to reduce physical strain on the pregnant partner, providing emotional support, and participating in healthcare decision-making.

The average age of respondents was 34.2 ± 7.3 years, with a considerable portion having finished secondary school education. This could indicate increased health literacy, as revealed in a 2018 study on education and health (17). Almost all of the respondents were married, and their marriages were monogamous, indicating a solid family structure. The majority of respondents make more than the minimum salary, indicating a reasonable level of financial stability, which may impact their access to healthcare services and ability to be more involved in their spouses' pregnancy and birth. This is consistent with a 2016 Nigerian study that found that women who thought receiving cash for treatment was not a significant deal were more likely to have the recommended number of ANC visits (18).

More than two-thirds of respondents were knowledgeable about pregnancy and delivery care, including potential difficulties. This is comparable to a 2019 study in India, which found that males with better information about pregnancy risks are more willing to participate in maternal health care (19). It is therefore necessary to continue to educate male partners in order to increase their understanding and involvement. Similarly, male commercial motorcyclists showed a good attitude toward pregnancy and delivery concerns. This indicates increased support for maternal health, which would result in improved mother and child health outcomes.

The majority of respondents in this survey were actively involved in various elements of antenatal care. The majority paid for ANC costs, which are critical in ensuring that pregnant moms receive the required medical care. Furthermore, more than half of the men attended ANC consultations with their wives,

indicating a strong level of cooperation and partnership in maternal health. More than half of respondents reminded their spouses about prescriptions, which is another sort of active involvement that helps people stick to their treatment programs. Almost half of the males were present during their child's birth, which was both emotionally reassuring for the mother and provided practical support by allowing healthcare workers to respond rapidly to any issues that may emerge during delivery. This conclusion is consistent with a comparable study conducted in Kenya (20). Furthermore, the majority of men provide transportation for their wife during delivery and save money to support the delivery process. These activities demonstrate a sense of responsibility and support for providing safe and comfortable delivery experiences. Despite their general engagement, only a tiny percentage of responders made arrangements for blood in case of an emergency during their wives' delivery. There is a significant gap in birth preparedness and complication readiness programs for reducing maternal mortality (7).

This study found that knowledge, attitude, and family type were all connected with male engagement in pregnancy and delivery care. Men in monogamous partnerships were around two and a half times more likely to actively participate in pregnancy and delivery care than men in polygamous relationships. However, attitude and knowledge were not statistically significant at the multivariate level of analysis. These findings underscore the importance of targeted treatments that take family type into account in order to encourage male participation and support throughout pregnancy and delivery. Age, marital status, and education were not associated with male engagement in pregnancy and delivery care in the study population. This may imply that broader measures are required to increase male engagement across all socio-demographic groups. A study conducted in Ethiopia identified several socio-cultural barriers that prevent male partners from assisting their spouses in accessing institutional delivery, including the belief that childbirth is a natural phenomenon that should not be given much attention and that these are exclusively female responsibilities (21).

The study's focus on commercial motorcyclists, a more economically engaged and younger male demographic, sheds light on the patterns and predictors of male involvement in maternal health. This cohort, which is frequently disregarded in maternal health studies, could serve as a model group for increasing male engagement in pregnancy and delivery care in the informal sector. The findings of this study should be interpreted in light of several limitations. Because the study only looked at

one occupational group, the results may not be fully applicable to other populations. The study's cross-sectional design also makes it difficult to examine changes in male involvement over time, limiting insights into causal linkages. Furthermore, the use of self-reported data may result in response bias, as individuals may overstate their supportive activities.

Conclusion

The study found a high level of male involvement in pregnancy and delivery care, which has the potential to improve mother and child health outcomes. While financial and logistical assistance is robust, targeted education is required to improve outcomes, particularly in the area of birth emergency preparedness. Policy proposals include personalized interventions that promote couple-based ANC education, as well as community awareness initiatives to increase male participation and create a more supportive atmosphere for maternal health. Further research might use a longitudinal method to investigate the factors that influence male involvement, with an emphasis on how to encourage more comprehensive participation in mother and child health.

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Conflict of interest

There is no potential conflict of interest to declare.

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